

**EXAMINING PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT ATTITUDES AND
PSYHOSOCIAL EFFECTS
IN PARENTS OF CHILDREN WITH CANCER: SOCIAL SUPPORT,
COPING ATTITUDES AND COMPASSION FATIGUE**

Şule AKSOY,

MSc, (Corresponding Author), Department of Family Education and Counseling,
Institute of Educational Sciences, Dokuz Eylül University, İzmir Türkiye; e-
mail: pd.suleaksoy@gmail.com, ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7336-0945

Hatice Zekavet KABASAKAL,

Prof. Dr., Department of Family Education and Counseling, Institute
of Educational Sciences, Dokuz Eylül University, İzmir Türkiye; e-
mail: zekavetkabasakal@gmail.com, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3450-1060

Abstract

The aim of the study is to examine the relationships between perceived social support, compassion fatigue, coping attitudes, attitudes toward seeking psychological help, and personality traits among parents of children with cancer. The study was conducted using a mixed-method approach, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative dimension was conducted with a total of 53 parents. In the qualitative dimension, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 5 parents.

Quantitative findings indicate that compassion fatigue is higher among parents with low levels of extroversion and emotional stability. It has been concluded that as the level of social support increases, functional coping strategies are used more frequently and attitudes toward seeking psychological help become more positive. Significant negative correlations were found between compassion fatigue and dysfunctional coping strategies, and positive correlations between compassion fatigue and functional coping strategies. Qualitative findings indicate that parents experience intense denial, shock, and loss of function when their children are first diagnosed, but as the treatment process progresses, they focus on their children's care and put their own self-care needs second. It has been observed that the support participants receive, particularly from their immediate circle and children, plays a supportive role in their coping skills during this process.

The findings indicate a need for interventions aimed at providing psychosocial support to parents, developing their coping skills, and strengthening their social support networks.

Keywords: Compassion fatigue, parents of children with cancer, childhood cancer, caregivers.

Introduction

Cancer is considered a significant public health problem today due to its prevalence in society and its high mortality rate (Turkish Cancer Research and Control Association [TCRCA], n.d.). Cancer affects millions of people worldwide in various ways. When statistics published by various institutions are examined, a high number of new cases are added to existing cases each year. Cancer types that occur between the ages of 0 and 15 are called childhood cancers. Childhood cancers (CC) are most commonly seen in children under the age of 5 and in the 10-15 age group. According to data released by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), more than 400,000 children and

adolescents (aged 0-19) worldwide are diagnosed with cancer each year. In Turkey, an average of 4,700 children and adolescents aged 0-19 are diagnosed with new CC cases each year (Turkish Ministry of Health, 2023).

Although CC accounts for a relatively low percentage of all cancer types globally, the financial, psychological, and physical burden experienced by children with cancer and their families during the disease process cannot be overlooked. Parents caring for children with cancer often face difficulties in these areas.

Parents of children with cancer (PCC) are generally assumed to be the primary caregivers of their children during their treatment. This situation raises concerns that parents may experience emotional exhaustion and detachment due to the significant caregiving burden placed upon them, as they are constantly engaged in caregiving activities throughout this process. It also raises concerns that they may experience compassion fatigue due to witnessing prolonged suffering.

It is of great psychosocial and preventative importance for parents to receive social support from their surroundings throughout the treatment and follow-up process. Social support can help individuals solve problems they encounter in various areas more effectively; it can prevent potential problems that individuals may experience (Ardahan, 2006). When evaluated from these perspectives, social support emerges as a powerful resource for protecting an individual's mental health. Coping attitudes reflect the types of behaviors and thoughts individuals resort to when faced with situations that threaten their well-being. The coping attitudes individuals adopt in the face of difficult life situations can be seen as related to personality traits. The formation and development of personality can be shaped by various factors such as the parents' mindset, parenting attitudes, and the life events experienced by the individual (Çiçek and Aslan, 2020).

The aim of this study is to contribute to the relevant literature by examining the relationship between the perceived levels of social support, compassion fatigue levels, coping attitudes, attitudes toward seeking psychological help, and personality traits of parents whose children have cancer, and to shed light on psychosocial support studies to be developed for parents whose children have cancer.

Method

This study aims to determine the perceived levels of social support, attitudes toward receiving psychological help, coping attitudes, compassion fatigue levels, and personality traits of PCC and to examine the relationship between them. For this purpose, the study was

conducted using a mixedmethod design. A mixed method is a research design that includes quantitative and qualitative data within a single study, and where both designs are used together (Gay et al., 2012).

The study population consists of parents living in Turkey whose children have cancer. Purposeful sampling was used in the sample selection. Parents participated in the study on a voluntarybasis. The sample of the study consists of parents who reside in the province of İzmir or whose children are being treated/have been treated at a hospital in the province of İzmir. A total of 53 parents participated in the study.

In this study, the Personal Information Form, the Multidimensional Perceived Social Support Scale (MPSS), Attitude Scale Towards Seeking Psychological Help-Short Form (ASTSPH-SF), Coping Attitudes Assessment Scale (COPE-R), Compassion Fatigue Scale (CFS), and Big Five-50 Personality Test (B5PT) were used as quantitative data collection tools; The semi-structured interviewmethod was used as a qualitative data collection tool.

IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0 software was used to analyze the data obtained in the research. In line with the purpose of the study, Pearson correlation analysis was applied to examine the relationships between the basic variables. Within the scope of this analysis, linear relationships between the variables of compassion fatigue, perceived social support, coping attitudes, attitudes toward seeking psychological help, and personality traits were evaluated. The qualitative data of the study were analyzed using the thematic analysis method. Thematic analysis is a qualitative analysis method that involves processes such as creating themes from qualitative data, interpreting themes, and reporting them (Braun and Clarke, 2021; cited in Hıncız and Yavuz, 2023).

In this study, the internal consistency Cronbach's Alpha value of the Compassion Fatigue Scale was .85, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the Coping Attitudes Assessment Scale was .74, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the Multidimensional Perceived Social Support Scale was .96, and the Cronbach's Alpha value of the Attitudes Toward Seeking Psychological Help Scale was .86. The Cronbach's Alpha values for the Big Five-50 Personality Test were calculated as .80 for extraversion, .70 for agreeableness, .50 for conscientiousness, .50 for emotional stability, and .72 for openness to experience.

Results

The table below examines the relationship between compassion fatigue and personality traits.

Table 1.

Five-factor personality traits according to compassion fatigue attitudes

Personality Trait	Compassion Fatigue	Mean	SS	t(51)	P
Extraversion	Absent	32.10	5.64	2.18	.034*
	Present	27.71	8.41		
Compatibility	Absent	37.51	5.74	.79	.434
	Present	36.00	7.26		
Responsibility	Absent	39.13	5.94	-1.44	.156
	Present	41.71	5.25		
Emotional Stability	Absent	30.87	6.42	2.76	.008*
	Present	25.21	7.03		
Openness to Development	Absent	34.62	4.97	-.45	.657
	Present	35.43	7.86		

When examining the relationship between compassion fatigue and personality traits, a negative and significant relationship is observed between compassion fatigue and extraversion. This finding suggests that individuals who are less extroverted may have higher levels of compassion fatigue. In this case, it is thought that individuals with an extroverted personality structure may have more sources of social support and a high readiness to receive social support. It was determined that the extraversion and emotional stability scores of individuals who did not experience compassion fatigue were significantly higher than those of individuals who experienced compassion fatigue.

The table examining the relationship between perceived social support level and compassion fatigue is presented below.

Table 2.

Correlations between compassion fatigue and perceived social support subdimensions

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
Compassion Fatigue	-				
Family Support	-.279*	-			
Special Person Support	-.075	.722**	-		
Peer Support	-.304*	.645**	.652**	-	
MPSS Total	-.255	.890**	.884**	.878**	-

A negative relationship has been observed between perceived family support and perceived peer support and compassion fatigue. This suggests that social support is a protective factor against compassion fatigue.

The table below contains the qualitative findings of the study. Qualitative findings are discussed for each variable.

Table 3.

Main themes and subthemes identified

Main Themes	Sub Themes	Frequency	Sample Participant Statements
Diagnosis Memories and Initial Reactions	1. Denial and Shock	5	“It was a total collapse... I couldn’t believe it for 15 days.” (K2)
	2. Somatic Responses and Functional Loss	7	“I couldn’t accept it at first...” (K3)
Lack of Support and Support Resources	1. Social Restriction - Restructuring	10	“After 20 days, you won’t have any friends left.” (K2)
	2. Approach to Psychological Support - Transportation Difficulties	5	“Blood ties aren’t as close as shared troubles.” (K2)
	3. Support Received from the Child and the Environment	13	“My daughter was the reason I stayed strong.” (K3)
Lack of Self-Care and Self-Neglect	1. Putting Yourself Second and Neglecting Your Personal Needs	10	“I don’t have the opportunity to get sick and take time off... I don’t deal with myself.” (K1)
	2. Neglecting Personal Care and Health	6	“I’ve never even thought about making time for myself.” (K2)
The Emotional Burden of the Process	1. Uncertainty and Anxiety About the Future	11	“I can’t fight anymore... The entire burden is on me, it’s very difficult.” (K5)
	2. Burnout from Excessive Responsibility	6	“The uncertainty of the future is frightening.” (K2, K4)
	3. Suppression and Internalization of Emotions	8	“We always strive to be strong like this so

that we can
be enough for
our children” (K2)

Qualitative findings reveal that parents experience intense denial, shock, and functional impairment in the initial period after their child's cancer diagnosis. Participants' statements indicate intense emotional reactions such as “collapse,” “disbelief,” and “freezing” at the moment of diagnosis. Additionally, somatic symptoms (e.g., insomnia, crying, feeling a heavy burden) and functional impairment are also prominent features of this period. This intense emotional process can be considered an important factor explaining the development of compassion fatigue (Uslu and Korkmaz, 2017). The majority of participants stated that while prioritizing their responsibilities for their children's care, they put their own self-care needs second and neglected their health. The statement, “He/She comes first, everything for him/her, then me” (K2) clearly reveals parents' tendency to put themselves last. This situation can become a factor that increases emotional and physical exhaustion in the long term, feeding compassion fatigue. Additionally, in qualitative themes, the uncertainty of the process, the fear of losing the child, and the weight of responsibilities emerge as significant factors increasing the emotional burden on parents. “What scares me most about this process is the fear... Yes, this process will pass somehow, but what if it happens again?” (K4) This statement shows how challenging it is to cope with anxiety and uncertainty. These findings support that parents experience a shared emotional burden, with intense anxiety, exhaustion, and self-neglect behaviors underlying compassion fatigue, despite no significant differences being found in quantitative analyses.

When examining participants' levels of social support, it was found that male participants' perceived social support scores were significantly higher than those of female participants. The table below examines perceived levels of social support and personality traits.

Table 4.

Correlations between perceived levels of social support and five-factor personality traits

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Family	-	.72 2**	.645* *	.890 **	.410* *	.267	.276* *	.086	.458* *
2. Special Person		-	.652* *	.884 **	.446* *	.311* *	.287* *	.216	.378* *
3. Friend			-	.878 **	.448* *	.277* *	.241	.208	.447* *

4.PerceivedSocial Support Status	-	.492*	.321*	.302*	.192	.486*
5.Extroversion	-	.579*	.164	.443*	.351*	
6.Compatibility	-	.494*	.424*	.414*		
7.Responsibility	-	.190	.426*			
8.EmotionalStability	-	.050				
9.Openness to Development	-					

Correlation analyses have revealed meaningful and positive relationships between perceived social support and personality traits. In particular, individuals with high scores in extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and intelligence/imagination were found to have high levels of perceived social support. When examining the subscales of perceived social support, similar positive relationships were found between family, support from a special person, and peer support and these personality traits. Similarly, self-help and approach-focused coping strategies also showed positive relationships with extraversion and openness to experience.

Qualitative findings show that parents experienced significant changes in their social environment and, in some cases, a belief that they were being harmed by their environment, a feeling of being misunderstood, and social restrictions led to a decrease in support resources. Participants' statements reveal an increased tendency to distance themselves, particularly in relationships with their immediate environment: "I completely distanced myself from people who drained my energy. I didn't even see my own mother and father... I didn't answer their calls." (K3). However, it is understood that one of the most important sources of support for parents is their children. The statement, "My son always monitored me... My son was always the one who supported me" (K2), emphasizes the mutual support that develops through the parent-child relationship.

Parents also benefit from resources such as support from spouses, relatives, or friends. Relationships formed with other parents in the hospital environment have created a new social support network: "The mothers here feel like sisters to me... It's not blood ties, but shared hardship that brings us closer." (K2). These findings show that social support is strengthened not only by the existing environment but also by new bonds formed with individuals who share similar experiences.

When quantitative and qualitative findings are evaluated together, it can be said that the diversity of social support resources is closely related to personality traits and individual coping skills.

Correlation analyses conducted to examine the relationship between attitudes toward seeking psychological help and personality traits indicate that there is no significant relationship between attitudes toward seeking psychological help and personality traits. However, the relationship between intelligence and imagination and the attitude toward seeking psychological help was found to be close to the threshold of significance. Qualitative findings reveal that the vast majority of parents do not seek psychological support and offer various reasons for this. The statement, "I never considered seeking support or taking medication. Because you look at all mothers' situations and they are the same, and we are mothers, so we are natural-born psychologists" (K2) indicates that cultural and personal beliefs may influence the decision to seek help. Similarly, practical obstacles such as financial constraints and lack of time are also among the prominent reasons: "I thought a lot about getting psychological support... but as I said, due to financial constraints... I couldn't find the opportunity, I still haven't found it." (K3). Some participants, however, stated that although they believed in the benefits of psychological support, they were unable to receive it due to the current responsibilities brought on by their child's illness: "I can't just leave everything behind right now because I have a little girl... I would need to do some research, but of course I feel it would be good for me." (K4). These statements indicate that attitudes toward seeking help are shaped not only by personal inclinations but also by caregiving burden, time management, and economic conditions. When quantitative and qualitative findings are evaluated together, it can be concluded that attitudes toward seeking psychological help are generally moderate, but can change positively with education level and individual awareness. Although most parents need support, they do not seek it, revealing that they face barriers to seeking help due to the burden of care and financial difficulties.

Correlation analyses conducted to examine the relationship between coping attitudes and personality traits indicate a positive and significant relationship between coping attitude and intelligence/imagination. Additionally, self-help-oriented coping attitudes are positively associated with extroversion and intelligence/imagination. These findings suggest that creative and extroverted individuals may be more likely to use functional coping strategies. Qualitative findings reveal that parents initially reacted with intense denial, shock, and numbness upon diagnosis, but as the process progressed, they focused on caring for their children and fulfilling their responsibilities: "I've learned to take control. I just do it. I don't think about myself... I do

what needs to be done.” (K1). These statements reveal parents' automatic responsibility behaviors in the coping process. Most parents put their own needs second and neglect their self-care for the sake of their children's health and well-being: “First him, him in everything. Him financially, him emotionally, then me.” (K2). This situation suggests that some parents have developed a self-neglecting approach rather than adaptive coping strategies.

The table examining perceived social support and coping attitudes is presented below.

Table 5.
Correlations between perceived social support and coping attitudes

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Family Support	-									
2. Special Person Support	.722**	-								
3. Friend Support	.645**	.652*	-							
4. MPSS Total	.890**	.884*	.878*	-						
5. Self-Help	.633**	.393*	.496*	.577*	-					
6. Approach	.328*	.341*	.379*	.397*	.434*	-				
7. Adaptation	.141	.103	.126	.140	.012	.256	-			
8. Avoidance	-.095	.021	-.198	-.110	.121	-.114	-.248	-		
9. Self-Punishment	-.228	-.117	-.227	-.219	.015	.075	-.219	.577*	-	
10. Coping Attitude	.291*	.277*	.227	.298*	.588*	.669*	.337*	.445*	.562**	-

The findings of the correlation analysis examining perceived social support and coping attitudes indicate that there are significant relationships between perceived social support and coping attitudes. It has been observed that as family and friend support increases, self-help and approach-focused coping strategies also strengthen. This result shows that social support resources are a factor that supports coping skills. When quantitative and qualitative findings are evaluated together, it is seen that the majority of parents act with a sense of responsibility, but put their own needs on the back burner.

When the findings are evaluated overall, it is seen that parents' personality traits do not show significant differences according to demographic factors, but dimensions such as extraversion, emotional stability, and intelligence/imagination are related to the perception of

social support and coping attitudes. The fact that parents experiencing compassion fatigue have lower levels of extraversion and emotional stability suggests that these traits may be protective factors.

Quantitative findings have revealed a significant negative relationship between coping attitudes and compassion fatigue in parents of children with cancer. This result suggests that parents with stronger coping skills may have lower levels of compassion fatigue. Specifically, a negative relationship was found between the self-help attitude, which is one of the functional coping strategies, and compassion fatigue, while positive and significant relationships were found with the self-punishment and avoidance/escape attitudes, which are dysfunctional coping strategies. This finding suggests that ineffective coping styles may have an exacerbating effect on compassion fatigue. When examined from a theoretical perspective, this result is consistent with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) Coping with Stress Model. As in the model, some coping methods may provide short-term relief but can have negative effects in the long term.

It has been observed that the perceived level of social support is related to both coping attitudes and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. It has been found that as the level of social support increases, self-help and approach-focused coping strategies are used more frequently, and attitudes toward seeking psychological help also become more positive. A moderate positive relationship was found between the attitude toward seeking psychological help and peer support. This finding indicates that social support resources may be a factor that strengthens the search for psychological help. When this situation is evaluated in terms of application, it is thought that the support parents involved in the individual or group psychological counseling process will receive in terms of strengthening their social support networks will help individuals discover effective support resources they can turn to in both professional and social areas. In the qualitative interviews in our current study, it was observed that one of the most important factors increasing participants' level of "acceptance" was their religious beliefs. It can be considered that individuals with strong religious beliefs frequently resort to religious coping as a coping method, and that this type of coping has protective and preventive functions in various ways.

When examining the relationship between compassion fatigue and perceived social support, it was found that as family and friend support increased, levels of compassion fatigue decreased significantly. However, it was determined that the relationship between total social support score and compassion fatigue did not reach a level of significance. It is thought that support provided by the immediate social circle may be more effective in alleviating the

emotional burden on parents. This suggests that the source and nature of social support are more important than the amount of support provided. Qualitative findings support this result. Participants frequently emphasized the support they received from those closest to them (spouse, children, close friends, etc.); they rarely mentioned types of support from their wider circle. Some parents stated that the support they received from their children helped them stay strong during this process: "My son was always the one who supported me... I couldn't have managed otherwise, we laughed together." (K2). "We are going through this process together, but my mother is more supportive, as are my friends. My friends, my coworkers, my friends at the hospital and my friends in my social life, I feel good support from them." (K4). These statements demonstrate the importance of perceived social support in the coping process and its preventive role.

In conclusion, the diversity and effective use of social support resources can positively influence both coping attitudes and the tendency to seek psychological help, thereby contributing to a reduction in compassion fatigue levels. It is understood that parents who develop functional coping strategies and benefit from social support are better able to manage their emotional burdens, and as a result, their compassion fatigue levels may be lower. Conversely, parents who lack support, neglect themselves, and use dysfunctional coping strategies may be considered a higher-risk group in terms of compassion fatigue.

Discussion

Fifty-three participants whose children had cancer participated in the study. Forty-five of the participants were women and eight were men. It is observed that the participation rate of male participants is significantly lower than that of female participants. The study included 53 participants whose children had cancer. Of these participants, 45 were women and 8 were men. It is observed that the participation rate of male participants is significantly lower than that of female participants. At the same time, when examining the qualitative data of the study, it is noteworthy that all participants in the semi-structured interviews were women. This situation is thought to create limitations in examining the relationship between variables and gender. Similarly, since 52 of the 53 participants were married, the study does not provide information about single or divorced parents. It can be said that assessments of the relationship between marital status and other variables are limited. When examining data on participants' educational background, it is observed that participants' educational levels are concentrated in middle school, high school, and university education levels; only 5 participants have elementary

school education, and 3 participants have postgraduate degrees. According to the Turkish Statistical Institute [TSI]'s national education statistics for 2024, the percentage of higher education graduates in Turkey is 25.3%. Among the participants in the study, this rate is 41.5%. In this case, it can be said that the educational level of the participants is above the Turkish average. When examining their employment status, it is seen that 60% of the participants are not currently working. This situation may be related to parents being the primary caregivers during their children's illness and the fact that 54.7% of participants had to leave their jobs because they had to relocate or commute for their children's treatment.

Quantitative findings have revealed a significant negative relationship between coping attitudes and compassion fatigue in parents of children with cancer. This result suggests that parents with stronger coping skills may have lower levels of compassion fatigue. Specifically, a negative relationship was found between the self-help attitude, which is a functional coping strategy, and compassion fatigue, while positive and significant relationships were found with the self-punishment and avoidance/escape attitudes, which are dysfunctional coping strategies. This finding suggests that ineffective coping styles may have an exacerbating effect on compassion fatigue. When examined from a theoretical perspective, this result is consistent with Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) Stress Coping Model. As in the model, some coping methods may cause short-term relief but can have negative effects in the long term. Similarly, in their study examining the coping styles of mothers with children undergoing cancer treatment, Ghaljeh and colleagues (2024) concluded that the various coping methods used by mothers and their frequent use of social support resources were factors that reduced compassion fatigue. However, Orbay and colleagues (2022) concluded in their study with the PCC that some parents experience compassion fatigue despite having high levels of social support, and that social support and coping strategies are not always protective factors against compassion fatigue. This suggests that the quality of perceived social support is more important than its quantity in its preventive role. It is thought that the effect of social support on individuals may vary depending on the individual's perception, their capacity to receive social support, and the type of support provided.

It has been observed that the perceived level of social support is related to both coping attitudes and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. As the level of social support increases, self-help and approach-oriented coping strategies are used more frequently, and attitudes toward seeking psychological help also become more positive. In particular, a moderate positive relationship was found between peer support and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. This finding indicates that social support resources may be a factor that

strengthens the search for psychological help. When evaluated in terms of application, it is thought that the support parents involved in individual or group psychological counseling processes will receive in strengthening their social support networks will help individuals discover effective support resources they can turn to in both professional and social areas. It has been observed that the perceived level of social support is related to both coping attitudes and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. As the level of social support increases, self-help and approach-oriented coping strategies are used more frequently, and attitudes toward seeking psychological help become more positive. In particular, a moderately positive relationship was found between peer support and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. This finding suggests that social support resources may be a factor that strengthens the search for psychological help. When evaluated from an application perspective, it is thought that the support parents participating in individual or group psychological counseling processes will receive in strengthening their social support networks will help individuals discover effective support resources they can turn to in both professional and social areas. Parents have indicated that the support they receive from healthcare professionals and family counseling is extremely helpful in coping with stress (Marfo et al., 2024). In another study conducted with caregivers of children with cancer, it was found that caregivers frequently used active coping and self-distraction coping strategies, planning and acceptance strategies were often functional in reducing anxiety, and faith-based coping was functional in depression (Joshi et al., 2025). The fact that the study was conducted in India requires consideration of the differences that cultural characteristics may bring. In the qualitative interviews in our current study, it was seen that one of the most important factors increasing participants' level of "acceptance" was their religious beliefs. It can be considered that individuals with strong religious beliefs frequently resort to religious coping as a coping method, and that this type of coping has protective and preventive functions in various ways.

When examining the relationship between compassion fatigue and perceived social support, it was found that as family and friend support increased, levels of compassion fatigue decreased significantly. However, it was determined that the relationship between total social support score and compassion fatigue did not reach a significant level. It is thought that support provided by the immediate social circle may be more effective in alleviating the emotional burden of parents. This suggests that the source and quality of social support are more important than the amount of support. Qualitative findings support this result. Participants frequently emphasized the support they received from those closest to them (spouse, children, close friends, etc.); they rarely mentioned types of support from their distant social environment.

Some parents stated that the support they received from their children helped them stay strong during this process: "My son was always there to support me... I couldn't have managed otherwise, we laughed together." (K2). "We're going through this process together, but my mom is more supportive, and so are my friends. My friends, and also my work colleagues, you know, my friends at the hospital and my friends in my social life, I feel good support from them." (K4). These statements demonstrate the importance of perceived social support in the coping process and its preventive role.

In conclusion, the diversity and effective use of social support resources can positively influence both coping attitudes and the tendency to seek psychological help, thereby contributing to a reduction in compassion fatigue levels. It is understood that parents who develop functional coping strategies and benefit from social support are better able to manage their emotional burdens, and as a result, their compassion fatigue levels may be lower. Conversely, parents who lack support, neglect themselves, and use dysfunctional coping strategies may be considered a higher-risk group in terms of compassion fatigue.

Recommendations for future studies and intervention programs to be developed are listed below.

1. Expansion of Psychosocial Support Programs: To reduce compassion fatigue among parents of children with cancer, it is recommended that psychological support programs, group therapy, and counseling services be offered in hospitals and oncology centers.

2. Training Programs to Strengthen Coping Skills: It is recommended to organize psycho-educational programs aimed at teaching parents stress management, emotional regulation, and effective coping strategies.

3. Developing Social Support Networks: Awareness campaigns should be conducted to strengthen support mechanisms among family, relatives, friends, and other caregivers. Support groups can be established where parents experiencing similar situations in the hospital environment can come together.

4. Increasing Parents' Self-Care Awareness: Considering that neglecting self-care can increase compassion fatigue, informative studies can be conducted to educate parents on the importance of not neglecting themselves.

5. Supporting Attitudes Toward Seeking Psychological Help: Free or low-cost services that facilitate access to psychological support can be expanded to overcome barriers such as financial constraints, lack of time, and lack of belief.

6. The Role of Healthcare Professionals: Training programs can be offered to professional groups such as nurses, psychologists, and social workers to equip them with the knowledge and skills to recognize parents' emotional burdens and provide the necessary guidance.

7. Personality-Sensitive Interventions: Parents who are more introverted and have lower emotional stability may be at risk for compassion fatigue. Intervention programs can provide individualized support by taking personality traits into account.

8. Replication of Research Studies: Longitudinal studies with larger sample groups will contribute to a better understanding of the factors affecting compassion fatigue.

9. Work Life and Flexible Arrangements: Work-life balance can be supported by providing flexible working hours or care leave for working parents.

10. Social Awareness Initiatives: Informing the public about the burden and difficulties experienced by families of children with cancer can contribute to increased social support.

References

Ardahan, M. (2006). Social support and nursing. *Anadolu Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences*, 9(2), 68-75.

Çiçek, İ., & Aslan, A. E. (2020). Personality and five-factor personality traits: A theoretical framework. *Batman University Journal of Life Sciences*, 10(1), 137-147.

Folkman, S., & Lazarus, R. S. (1985). If it changes it must be a process: Study of emotion and coping during three stages of a college examination. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 48(1), 150-170.

Gay, L.R., Mills, G.E., Airasian, P.W. (2012). Educational research: competencies for analysis and application. 10th Edition, Pearson, Upper Saddle River.

Ghaljeh, M., Pezaro, S., & Mardani-Hamooleh, M. (2024). Mothers' efforts to overcome difficult twists and turns in living with children with cancer: A phenomenological study. *BMC Women's Health*, 24(1), 3295.

Hınız, G., & Yavuz, A. (2023). Reflective thematic analysis: An example from a doctoral dissertation. *Theory and Practice in Education*, 19(2), 388-408.

Joshi, P., Gopichandran, L., Agrawal, U.S., Garg, R & Tiwari, S.K. (2025). Psychological distress and coping strategies among caregivers of children with cancer: A cross-sectional study. *Encancer Medical Science*, 13(19).

Marfo, M., Acheampong, A. K., David, D.A. & Aziato, L. (2024). Coping strategies adapted by parents caring for children with cancer: A qualitative exploratory study in Ghana. *Discover Psychology*, 4(84).

Orbay, İ., Baydur, H., & Uçan, G. (2022). Compassion fatigue in informal caregivers of children with cancer; a section from Turkey. *Social Work in Public Health, 37*(5), 395–408.

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Turkey. (2023). International Childhood Cancer Day. Retrieved December 11, 2024, from <https://hsgm.saglik.gov.tr/tr/haberler-kanser/uluslararasi-cocukluk-cagikanserleri-guenue.html>.

Turkish Cancer Research and Fight Association (n.d.). World cancer statistics. Retrieved December 10, 2024, from <https://www.turkkanser.org/uploads/dosyalar/istatistikler/dunya-kanseristatistikleri.pdf>.

Turkish Statistical Institute [TSI]. (2025) National Education Statistics, 2024. Access Address: <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Ulusal-Egitim-Istatistikleri-2024-53937>

Uslu, Y., & Korkmaz, F. (2017). The emotional side of nursing: Compassion fatigue. *Ege University Journal of Nursing Faculty, 33*(3), 133–140.